

1 Reframing human-nature relationships through art

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14

15 Abstract

16 Growing numbers of people engage in forms of nature stewardship within their private gardens.
17 Yet many ecological structures in gardens that support species, such as deadwood or stone piles,
18 rarely appear in public green spaces, in part because they conflict with prevailing landscape design
19 standards. Reimagining such structures as sculptures could help make them culturally legible and
20 open new ways of imagining how cultural processes can contribute to supporting biodiversity. To
21 explore this idea, we led a transdisciplinary project in which artists and biodiversity scientists co-
22 created sculptures designed to function as both artworks and habitats for species. We outline our
23 process and outcomes as an example of how art and science can explore the role of cultural and
24 societal processes, not merely as pressures from which nature must be protected, but also as
25 legitimate ecological processes capable of creating more, not less, nature.

26

27 Introduction

28 Modern Western thought on biodiversity is dominated by two concepts; one science-driven,
29 namely that humans are responsible for higher than baseline levels of species and ecosystem loss,
30 and one value-laden, a dualist mindset in which humans are not part of nature (Mace 2014;
31 Dussault 2016). Research and reflection on insidious human impacts has rightly prompted urgent
32 conservation action, yet the prevailing focus on destruction and loss has also fostered apathy and
33 alienation from nature (Knowlton 2017; Malavasi 2025). These ideas in turn filter into and shape
34 our cultural perceptions of nature, as well as our place in it. In response, art is increasingly used to
35 communicate scientific insights and foster emotional connection to the living world (Westley *et*
36 *al.* 2020; Scheffer *et al.* 2024). However, art should avoid merely reproducing narratives of crisis

37 or reinforcing human–nature separation. Otherwise, it risks constraining our ability to imagine
38 how humans, through participatory, creative cultural practices, can also support biodiversity. New
39 narratives need to show how humans, acting as part of nature, can also choose to shape the requisite
40 conditions for more and not less nature (Marris 2013; Reyers and Bennett 2025).

41 Gardens, in particular, exemplify spaces where cultural and ecological processes tangibly
42 converge, with changes in garden design reflecting changes in prevailing human–nature
43 connections (Teyssoit and Mosser 1991). This has shifted from a desire for domination over nature
44 in the 17th century, to a picturesque reconstruction of nature for human pleasure in the 18th and
45 19th century, to modernist and utilitarian forms in the 20th century. As human life becomes
46 increasingly detached from nature, and biodiversity loss enters mainstream discourse, gardens are
47 emerging as spaces where individuals seek to engage with biodiversity in their daily lives (Oh *et*
48 *al.* 2022). Especially in private gardens, ecologically-minded land stewardship is becoming
49 increasingly popular: from planting native species, building stone piles for reptiles, nesting sites
50 for birds, dry-stone walls for arthropods, to creating deadwood and compost heaps, or other
51 features that support declining animals and plants (Staude *et al.* 2025). This marked shift in
52 gardening ethos reflects not only a growing desire to contribute positively to biodiversity
53 conservation, but also a response to the increasing rarity of everyday nature experiences and a wish
54 to restore a sense of connection to the living world.

55 Yet this shift in gardening ethos remains in its infancy and is largely confined to the private realm.
56 Extending it into the public sphere represents both a challenge and an opportunity. Public green
57 spaces can be powerful settings for shaping collective narratives and everyday habits (Jugert *et al.*
58 2016); they signal which kinds of relationships between people and nature are possible and
59 desirable. In a rapidly urbanizing world, limited everyday exposure to and contact with nature
60 constrains our capacity to emotionally and culturally include non-human species (Langer *et al.*
61 2021; Cazalis *et al.* 2023). Therefore, public urban green spaces shape many human-nature
62 encounters and influence our values towards the living world. Currently, most urban landscapes
63 continue to prioritize tidy appearances that are less conducive to biodiversity than they could be,
64 even though more biodiverse designs would not limit practical human use (Yap *et al.* 2022).
65 Manicured and tidy spaces dominate over meadows and the presence of wild or decaying elements
66 that could support biodiversity. This divide between what is seen as beautiful and what supports
67 species limits how we imagine coexistence. Reframing this will be key to creating nature-positive
68 public spaces and offers us a chance to reimagine how creativity can foster more-than-human life.

69 It is unrealistic to expect that urban green spaces cater fully to the needs of non-human species
70 without regard for aesthetics or practical human requirements. However, we argue that this division
71 may also be unnecessary, with small shifts in focus lending themselves to a blend of culture and
72 nature (Fig. 1). Here, we focus on how sculptures can be reimaged as biodiversity-supporting
73 structures in public green spaces. We conducted a six-month project, *Living Sculptures*, during
74 which time biodiversity scientists and artists reinterpreted ecological garden structures such as
75 deadwood and nesting sites to appeal to both human and nonhuman audiences. The resulting works

76 were displayed as an art exhibition in the Leipzig Botanical Garden in Germany. With *Living*
77 *Sculptures* we wanted to reflect on the role and creative agency of humans, exemplifying our
78 potential to act as co-designers and stewards of living systems, whilst simultaneously offering a
79 different outlook to the prevailing “doom and gloom” narrative. In the following, we outline our
80 process, outcomes and learnings for use in future art–science collaborations and call for more
81 consideration and integration of ecology in public design.

82
83 **Fig. 1: Reimagining sculptures used in landscaping with biodiversity in mind.** (A) Bronze horses imitating
84 deadwood: such forms could be constructed from actual deadwood to provide habitat for arthropods and fungi. (B)
85 Human figure made of stones and metal: a similar structure placed in a sunny location could offer basking and shelter
86 sites for reptiles if connected to the soil. (C) Metal sculpture with perforations: could be built from stone, clay or loess
87 with cavities to serve as nesting sites for wild bees. (D) Plant sculpture of exotic species: could instead feature
88 regionally endangered or locally extinct native plants, allowing cities to articulate a cultural narrative in which
89 biodiversity is understood as part of local heritage and collective responsibility. (E) Colorful stacked sculpture: could
90 be reimagined as a functional compost structure. Photo credits: Ingmar Staude.

91 **The process of building transdisciplinary collaboration**

92 *Forming a consortium.* The *Living Sculptures* project was initially conceived by biodiversity
93 scientists, but a first priority was to establish an interdisciplinary consortium to prevent the project
94 from remaining siloed within science, and to build partnerships with institutions that could offer
95 the requisite complementary skills and capacities needed for the project. The Leipzig Botanical
96 Garden could provide both space and curatorial support, including workshop rooms, exhibition
97 space, marketing and outreach. We also partnered with the Leipzig-based wood-working atelier,
98 manufactur e.V., which provided workspace, machinery and material; resources that we deemed
99 relevant for our project. In addition, the atelier has a strong network of contacts to different city
100 offices, e.g., forestry and urban green and blue infrastructure department, which were consulted
101 throughout the project to obtain the necessary permissions to source natural materials. As the
102 project included an open call for artists, we invited a curator with previous experience in science-
103 art collaborations to join the consortium and assist with the selection process. Finally, we invited
104 a filmmaker who accompanied the project to document its process. Once the consortium was
105 formed, we applied for interdisciplinary project funding from the Cultural Office of the City of
106 Leipzig. Together with other funding sources (Leipzig Stiftung, Oak Spring Garden Foundation
107 and the botanical garden itself), we raised a total budget of approximately 20,000 euros.

108 *Open call to artists.* In February 2025, we launched an open call for five artists from Leipzig and
109 the surrounding region to participate in the project (Material 1). To reach potential applicants, we
110 first compiled a mailing list of universities, art schools, and art collectives in the region. This list
111 was used for direct outreach. In addition, the call was publicized through the Botanical Garden's
112 social media channels and distributed as printed posters in various ateliers across Leipzig. Artists
113 were given a month to apply and were asked to submit a CV, a portfolio, and a short proposal
114 outlining an initial sculptural idea(s) for the project. By mid-March, we had received 48
115 applications. The consortium also served as the jury for evaluating submissions. Each application
116 was assessed according to five criteria scored from zero to ten: 1) relevance to the overall project
117 goals (integration of ecological and artistic design elements), 2) innovation and conceptual quality,
118 3) quality of previous work, 4) potential to enhance biodiversity, and 5) potential for
119 transdisciplinary and scientific collaboration. After individual scoring, the consortium met to
120 discuss a short-list of applicants and reached a consensus on the final selection. By the end of
121 March, the five selected artists were contacted, and all confirmed their participation.

122 *Collaborations and team building:* We organized two workshops designed around forming
123 collaborations between the scientists and artists. The first workshop took place on April 1st in the
124 Leipzig Botanical Garden and began with a series of icebreakers to create an open atmosphere.
125 Presentations then introduced the project's goals, scope, and ecological background, followed by
126 short talks from each artist in which they described their background and initial project ideas. After
127 the presentations, participants were given a guided tour of the botanical garden, which also served
128 as the exhibition site, with input from the ecologists that work there to ensure that the resulting
129 works would be informed by the needs and capacity of the site itself. The day concluded with a

130 “lightning round,” where artists were paired with scientists from the consortium and with invited
131 experts, such as those working on nesting structures for bees, whose expertise we considered
132 relevant for discussing initial ideas. The scientists rotated between the artists to offer feedback and
133 explore possible collaborations. Following the workshop, each artist received the contact details
134 of the scientists and was encouraged to continue consultations as needed. Scientists were meant to
135 act as facilitators, helping artists access specific knowledge or contacts within their networks. In
136 the period between the two workshops, four independent exchanges and consultations took place.

137 The second workshop took place on April 30th in the wood workshop atelier of manufactur e.V.
138 and focused on the artists’ revised sculpture ideas. This meeting had two main aims: to obtain
139 feedback from the consortium and the participating artists, and to discuss practical and logistical
140 aspects of implementation. The atelier provided technical guidance, including access to
141 woodworking equipment and support in sourcing deadwood required for several sculptures. The
142 consortium provided input on ecological aspects as well as organizational matters, including the
143 placement of sculptures within the botanical garden, transportation logistics, and installation
144 timelines. The group discussed curatorial considerations together. Artists also provided feedback
145 on each other’s work. For example, those working with metal provided guidance on material
146 choices and welding for projects that required structural support or fixation in the soil, while those
147 working with clay helped each other with questions about drying times and stability. The second
148 workshop furthered our aim of co-creation, as participants had by then formed a cohesive and
149 supportive team that worked together in a highly constructive way. The day concluded with a joint
150 potluck and informal gathering at the atelier space.

151 *Work period.* After the second workshop, the artists had another seven weeks before the exhibition
152 opening (June 21st) to work on their sculptures. During this time the project manager was the
153 central node of contact, addressing all logistical challenges (e.g., insurance, transport, installation,
154 licensing, permissions, marketing) and acting as a point of contact between the artists, scientists
155 and institutions. The film maker visited each artist's atelier space, conducted interviews with them
156 and the consortium, and worked on putting together a 20 minute documentary. This was also the
157 period when the consortium organized and implemented all curatorial aspects of the exhibition.
158 The full team including the artists contributed to a brochure, detailing the project aims and
159 individual pieces themselves (Material 2). QR codes on the artwork labels linked to further
160 information on the project page of the botanical garden website. From June 10th onwards, we
161 began installing and assembling the sculptures in the gardens. Some pieces were fully constructed
162 on-site at the Botanical Garden, while others could be transported there preassembled.
163 Considerations such as theft protection, visitor safety, and insurance against damage were also
164 important factors in our planning and budgeting. Lastly, the team organized a vernissage event,
165 and a press release announcing the exhibition was written together with and issued by the Leipzig
166 University press office and featured in several local newspapers.

167 **Sculptures and exhibition**

168 *Sculptures*. We concluded the project with a total of 14 sculptures. One sculpture designed by
169 “Gesellschaft für artübergreifende Freundschaft” (Society for Interspecies Friendship) called
170 *Traces*, reimagines the design of an entire habitat space (Fig. 2a). The sculpture incorporates
171 deadwood, clay and a pond, to allow animals and plants to have access to water and shelter, whilst
172 also making their movements visible on a wet clay surface. Another two sculptures were made by
173 Sarah Pschorn: one hour-glass, *RAR*, and one trellis-like structure, *Overgrow*, both made out of
174 fired clay (Fig. 2b). *RAR* houses a native plant species that is listed as extinct in the wild in
175 Germany, *Iberis amara*, which was placed in the tropical greenhouse of the botanical garden,
176 thereby inviting reflection on what counts as exotic today, suggesting that rare and declining native
177 plants may now fit this category. *Overgrow* acts as a garden trellis over which a non-native species,
178 *Phaseolus coccineus*, climbs and successively overgrows the sculpture, encouraging the viewer to
179 reflect on the aesthetic potential of wild, encroaching patches in gardens where humans relinquish
180 control. The *Living Spiral* was designed by Daniel Böttcher out of discarded oak beams and formed
181 into the shape of a spiral, or DNA helix, with sand and clay forming the base of the sculpture (Fig.
182 2c). The sand base and oak beams with cavities of varying depth and size provide nesting sites for
183 wild bees. Over time, as the bottom beams begin to decay and rot away, additional beams can be
184 added to the top. Sergey Karev designed *Maple Seed* in which yew deadwood trunks were
185 repurposed together with a metal structure (Fig. 2d), encouraging viewers to consider how
186 deadwood, often regarded as messy, might be combined with more inert materials like metal and
187 used as a valid form of art material. Nine additional sculptures were part of a series called
188 *Guardians* by Marie Ronniger, designed to reimagine and combine the look and purpose of
189 traditional garden gnomes, nesting sites and water holes for insects (Fig. 2e).

190 *Exhibition*. We opened the exhibition during the Long Night of Sciences at the Leipzig Botanical
191 Garden on June 21st. This annual summer solstice event invites the public to explore scientific
192 institutions across the city and is especially popular at the Botanical Garden. We chose this event
193 to ensure that many members of the public could experience the exhibition and to facilitate direct
194 exchange between the public, scientists, and artists. The vernissage was divided into several
195 smaller events. First, we held a smaller opening event just before the Long Night of Sciences
196 began, inviting journalists, city officials, and colleagues of the participating artists and scientists.
197 During the vernissage, members of the consortium gave introductory speeches presenting the
198 project and its participants, followed by guided tours led by the artists through their installations.
199 The event concluded with a public screening of the documentary (https://youtu.be/ix1zJ_CBxi4).
200 After the screening, the Long Night of Sciences officially began. Throughout the evening, both
201 scientists and artists jointly offered guided tours for visitors every hour until midnight.
202 Approximately 100 people attended the vernissage, and around 1,000 visitors experienced the
203 exhibition during the Long Night of Sciences. Although the artworks remain the property of the
204 individual artists, all, bar one, of the sculptures will remain in the Botanical Garden in perpetuity,
205 as we intend to monitor their role as habitat for species. It is estimated that 10,000 people will have
206 viewed the sculptures in the first year.

208

209 **Fig. 2: Living Sculptures.** (A) Traces is a habitat structure where dead wood surrounds a strip of moist clay that is
 210 connected to a small pool of water that is filled again with plants, stones and crevices for aquatic animals. On the clay
 211 surface one can observe traces of animals who went to the water pool. (B) Fired clay sculptures used as trellis
 212 overgrown by a climbing plant over time, and an hourglass sculpture in the green house with the German extinct
 213 species *Iberis amara*. (C) Helix out of oak dead wood on a sand and clay foot, both with nesting cavities for wild bees.
 214 As the wood rots away at the bottom, additional stacks can be added to the top. (D) Dead wood of yew on a metal

215 structure forming a shape resembling a maple seed dispersal unit. (E) Clay sculptures reminiscent of the German
216 garden gnome, with nesting structures and water puddles. Photo credits: Mim Schneider.

217 **Reflections and lessons learned**

218 With *Living Sculptures* we explored the wider idea that humans and cultural activities, as
219 ecological processes in their own right, can shape conditions for more, not less, nature (Marris
220 2013); an idea relevant to many areas of public life. For instance, plant sculptures (Fig. 1d) could
221 be composed of critically endangered native species and placed in a central public space, allowing
222 cities to put forward a cultural narrative in which biodiversity is understood as part of local heritage
223 and collective responsibility. In urban areas facing rising summer temperatures, sculptures could
224 fulfill aesthetic, climatic, and ecological functions simultaneously. That is, in locations where trees
225 cannot be planted, sculptures could provide shade by incorporating biodiversity, such as green
226 roofs with steppe vegetation or climbing plants. Prestigious landscape design projects could
227 incorporate stone sculptures that provide habitat for reptiles or commission artists to create and
228 maintain decaying, fungi-inoculated deadwood sculptures. Overall, there are myriad possibilities
229 to bring the arts and biodiversity together in designs that promote positive narratives of human
230 creativity within the biodiversity crisis in public spaces. In the following, we critically reflect on
231 our project in a bid to provide learnings for future art-science collaborations.

232 *Balancing open-ended exploration with specialized input.* In our project, both financial and
233 temporal resources for collaboration were relatively limited. Yet meaningful interdisciplinary
234 connections and knowledge sharing require time and breathing space to develop (Norström *et al.*
235 2020). We suggest providing ample time at the outset for the team to explore, discard, and integrate
236 new ideas into the design process, based on transdisciplinary discussions. This should include
237 open-ended and informal workshops in diverse settings, drawing on established co-creation
238 methods from different disciplines (e.g., the viewpoint method from theatre) to build trust and
239 understanding. Where possible, individuals skilled in such facilitation techniques should be
240 included in the consortium. However, such extended collaboration also benefits from a clear
241 structure. In the early stages, when ideas are still open-ended, a diversity of perspectives is
242 valuable. However, as concepts take shape, the focus should gradually shift toward more
243 specialized and targeted input. In our project, for instance, we invited a broad range of scientists
244 to the first workshop. However, given the already limited timeframe of the project, concrete
245 decisions regarding the sculpture designs had to be made quickly, and the diversity of ideas could
246 not be fully considered. More specific expertise on insect nesting habitats was required and
247 provided, however, practical expertise on deadwood ecology, for example, was missing and was
248 not rectified in time. Effective planning and facilitation therefore involve not only providing
249 enough time for collaboration but also knowing when to invite broad input and when to shift
250 towards focused expertise.

251 *Allowing science to be informed by art.* As in many science–art collaborations, it remains a
252 challenge to achieve genuine reciprocity rather than a one-sided process in which science provides
253 the information that artists translate into creative works (Scheffer *et al.* 2015; Bjordam and

254 Scheffer 2024). In our project, the initial idea came from the scientific side, which set a clear
255 direction early on. However, once artists joined, they developed their own concepts largely
256 independently, and the scientists acted to provide technical details and information only for some
257 but not all sculptures (e.g., regarding plant choice, dead wood, or nesting cavity dimensions).
258 While this can still be a productive process, the greater challenge lies in creating opportunities for
259 reciprocal learning, where scientists also take inspiration from the creativity, observation, and
260 methods of artists. We see two paths for this to happen. One is that scientists learn from the artistic
261 process and find ways to integrate it into their work, the other comes from the novel questions and
262 experiments that arise from the artistic products. The sculptures themselves offer promising
263 opportunities for reciprocal learning. For example, the spiral sculpture (Fig. 2c) could have served
264 as an experiment to explore how different tree species affect the nesting preferences of insects. In
265 retrospect, allocating resources for facilitating community science would have also enriched the
266 project by enabling documentation of species interactions with the artworks over time. Future
267 collaborations could therefore benefit from explicitly recognizing and planning for such
268 reciprocity in which artistic processes and products can inform scientific research.

269 *Strengthen art–science projects through cross-scientific collaboration.* Our experience also
270 showed that many artists already came with substantial ecological knowledge and conceptual ideas
271 of their own. In this sense, ecologists did not fundamentally change the sculptures that artists
272 conceived, but rather provided the framework within which artistic work could develop. Ideally,
273 the project would have included stronger scientific input on how to integrate novel ecological
274 knowledge into the sculptures. However, practical ecological guidance, such as how deep a nesting
275 cavity should be, often remains relatively straightforward, and is now increasingly accessible in
276 an age of large language models. Furthermore, research on biodiversity, coexistence, or ecosystem
277 functioning is frequently conducted under controlled experimental conditions that are difficult to
278 translate into relevant, real world contexts (Carpenter 1996; Scheffer *et al.* 2024). This could
279 change if co-creation becomes a stronger incentive in ecological and global change research
280 (Norström *et al.* 2020). Moreover, this situation could change if art–science collaborations also
281 became more interdisciplinary within the sciences themselves. For instance, in our project,
282 partnerships with material scientists could have informed artists about new substrates for habitats,
283 creating immediate experimental platforms where artists and scientists could exchange concepts
284 across disciplines and learn from one another. Bringing multiple scientific disciplines into dialogue
285 with the arts could create more applied and solution-oriented settings, broadening the possibilities
286 for science to inform the artistic process and for reciprocal learning to emerge.

287 *The future of funding, funding the future.* As a final, yet fundamental consideration, funding for
288 both science and culture is being drastically reduced across much of Europe. Germany, despite its
289 long-standing tradition of supporting both these pillars of civil society, is not immune to these
290 cutbacks. Moreover, there is generally little funding available specifically for transdisciplinary
291 work that bridges science and art. Finding suitable funding calls and securing sufficient support
292 was therefore difficult, which in itself keeps such projects rare and challenging. We call for more

293 funding schemes that explicitly enable and sustain this kind of collaboration. Despite funding
294 reductions, science still tends to be better funded than the arts, which suggests that scientific
295 programs could more often allocate resources for artistic collaboration. For example, scientific
296 synthesis initiatives, such as sDiv¹, SESYNC² or CESAB³, have shown how concentrated
297 collaboration can accelerate scientific discovery. Future synthesis formats could increasingly
298 engage with co-creation, in which scientists, artists, practitioners, and others collaborate on data
299 visualizations, participatory public artworks, urban biodiversity interventions, and education and
300 communication, thereby opening space for imaginative and applied approaches to shared
301 challenges.

302 **Toward co-creative earth stewardship**

303 The *Living Sculptures* project was motivated by the idea of examining how public art can support
304 biodiversity and present biodiversity conservation as an inclusive and participatory form of earth
305 stewardship, where cultural processes help create more, rather than less, nature. It explored how
306 ecological structures for wildlife in gardens and urban green spaces, often not designed with
307 aesthetics in mind, could be reimaged through the arts to become both functional and visually
308 engaging, and thus become more frequently used in public spaces. This presented creative
309 challenges for artists and invited collaboration with scientists. Ultimately, such collaborative
310 projects could stimulate new forms of garden and landscape design elements that are both
311 ecologically functional and aesthetically compelling. Incorporating such art into our urban green
312 spaces could show that culture and nature can and need to go hand in hand. We hope that our
313 workflow and the lessons we learned can support other projects pursuing co-creative forms of earth
314 stewardship.

315

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¹ <https://www.idiv.de/de/forschung/sdiv-synthesis-centre/>

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